

Chemistry of Lanthanons

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Acetoacetanilide complexes of transition metals¹⁻³ and Be⁴, Al and U⁵ had been studied extensively, but so far little has been reported about the complexes with lanthanons.

Having completed the works on β -diketonate of lanthanons, the work is now extended to the study of complexes of lanthanons with acetoacetanilide, its derivatives like 2-chloro acetoacetanilide, 2-methyl acetoacetanilide, and benzoacetanilide.

With acetoacetanilide, using our general method of preparation for β -diketonates⁶, complexes of the type $\left[\text{LnL}_2 \begin{matrix} \text{OH} \\ \text{H}_2\text{O} \end{matrix} \right]$ were obtained where L = PhNHCOCH₂COCH₃ and Ln = La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd and Y. The complexes have been characterised by chemical analysis and i.r. spectra which show definite presence of water molecules within. Thermal analysis of the complex of Nd shows one endothermic loss of weight upto temperature 130° which indicates loss of one molecule of water confirming the above composition.

During the progress of our work, Sen and others⁷ reported complexes of the type LnL₃, 2H₂O with the same ligand. Their method of preparation was, however, entirely different from ours.

EXPERIMENTAL

To an aqueous solution of the lanthanide nitrate (obtained from weighed amount of 99.9% oxide), a calculated amount of the ligand (mole ratio 1 : 3) in acetone-water (1 : 1) was added. The pH of the solution was raised to 7.5 with dil.NH₃ (1 : 4), when the complex precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with acetone-water (1 : 1) and recrystallised from acetone A.R. Using more of the ligand only bis complex was obtained.

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TABLE I

Analytical data for acetoacetanilide complexes $\left[\text{LnL}_2 \begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \text{H}_2\text{O} \end{array} \right]$

Ln	Colour	M.Pt.	% of Oxide		% of N	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
La	White	180°	31.20	31.0	5.27	5.3
Pr	Green	205°	32.46	32.5	4.90	5.2
Nd	Pink	193°	31.30	31.6	5.09	5.2
Sm	Cream	201°	32.46	32.4	5.10	5.2
Gd	White	Decomposes	32.90	33.2	4.90	5.2
Y	White	96°	18.15	18.3	6.70	6.8

The complexes with benzoacetanilide were found to have the tris-composition LnL_3 . With the other two ligands, 2-Cl and 2- CH_3 acetoacetanilide, the complexes of lanthanons, from the analytical data, corresponded to the bridged formula like $\text{L}_2\text{Ln} \begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \text{OH} \end{array} \text{LnL}_2$. Works on these complexes are in progress to establish their structures conclusively.

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